

Heterogeneous Integration of III-V Materials by Direct Wafer Bonding for High-Performance Electronics and Optoelectronics

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Abstract—III-V materials such as InGaAs and InP are highly attractive for high-performance electronics and optoelectronics owing to their high carrier mobilities and potential for band gap engineering. Integration on silicon substrates, however, is a key requirement to enable widespread adoption of these materials. In this work, direct wafer bonding (DWB) of III-V materials is explored as a low-temperature enabling technology for Si integration. For high-performance logic and RF electronics, DWB is compared to competing integration technologies, and is shown to exhibit the higher device performance due to its relatively low process complexity and thermal impact (~300 °C). Due to the low thermal impact of DWB, it is also uniquely suitable for 3D integration, i.e. vertical stacking of multiple functional layers. III-V optoelectronics are attractive in such 3D stacks, where they can enable high-efficiency tunable lasers together with Si photonics integrated circuits. DWB is here compared to selective epitaxy as an integration route for InP-on-Si microdisk lasers. Plasmonics are explored as well, allowing scaling of integrated III-V photonic devices beyond the diffraction limit of light. The results of this work show that DWB is a highly promising integration route for III-V materials for both electronics and optoelectronics applications.

Index Terms—III-V, MOSFET, 3D integration, plasmonics, optoelectronics, direct wafer bonding, selective epitaxy

I. Introduction

COMPOUND III-V semiconductor materials containing indium, such as $\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{As}$ and InP, have received significant research attention for their promising applications in both electronics and optoelectronics [1], [2]. Their high carrier mobilities make them suitable as channel materials in high-performance transistors, such as metal-oxide field-effect transistors (MOSFETs) and high electron mobility transistors (HEMTs) [3]. For logic applications, the high mobility can enable reduction of the operating bias, leading to lower power density in high-density logic circuits [4]–[6]. For high-frequency and low-noise applications, such as low-noise amplifiers (LNAs), the high mobility translates to both lower noise and higher gain [2], [7], [8]. By tuning the compound composition, III-V materials also enable band gap engineering,

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Fig. 1. Illustration of a 3D integrated system containing multiple functional layers combining silicon (logic and memory) and III-V (RF, photonics and sensing) functionalities to enable extremely compact and efficient systems.

complex heterostructures with tailored energy landscapes, which can lead to unique low-power devices such as tunneling FETs and quantized FETs [9], [10]. In optoelectronics applications, band gap engineering and direct band gaps are used to create active photonic devices such as tunable and highly efficient lasers [11]–[15]. An emerging challenge that III-V materials are well positioned to meet is the interconnect bottleneck in high data transfer systems [16]. Here, on-chip optical communication could improve bandwidth and speed and reduce power dissipation [17]. Fig. 1 shows a vision of a general heterogeneous 3D integrated system, with multiple layers supplying different functionalities such as logic, RF and photonics. To enable cost-efficient systems, not only tight integration between electronics and photonics is required, but also integration on silicon substrates. As these III-V materials are lattice mismatched to Si, numerous approaches have been explored for their integration [18]–[21]. While local integration of III-Vs using selective epitaxy is attractive for the ability to move to larger wafer sizes of silicon (relative to standard III-V wafer sizes) and high granularity of integration with Si devices, lattice mismatch poses a serious challenge in the direct growth of III-V on Si, as growth defects and strain relaxation can lead

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Fig. 2. Schematic illustrations of different heterogeneous integration schemes. (a) Basic integration by direct wafer bonding, here showing the formation of a blank III-V-on-insulator film on a Si substrate. (b) Sequential 3D integration results in a III-V device layer integrated on an already fabricated device layer, with high alignment accuracy between the two layers. (c) Single non-sequential 3D integration, i.e. integration of two already fabricated device layers. This approach yields a top layer that is flipped relative to the orientation of the original wafer. (d) By use of an intermediate transfer DWB step, the original orientation can be recovered in the final 3D stack. This will allow for more straightforward interconnect formation between the layers.

Fig. 3. (a) Binding energies for a few different DWB interfaces. The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ interface offers a strong interface bond at a relatively low temperature of only 250°C . (b) Schematic of a 3D integrated III-V MOSFET over Si CMOS stack, with a TEM image of the fabricated structure. These devices were integrated sequentially, yielding a high accuracy alignment between the two layers. (c) The subthreshold swing of the Si CMOS devices in the prior 3D stack before and after the full 3D integration process. The constant subthreshold swing before and after integration indicates that the sensitive oxide interface incurred no significant damage from the process.

to reduced carrier mobilities and poor material quality [22], [23]. In addition, such approaches rely on growth of III-V materials, which for integration with already fabricated device layers leads to a high thermal impact, typically around 500°C . In a 3D integrated layer stack such thermal impact can reduce the performance of lower level layers [24]. Layer transfer techniques such as direct wafer bonding (DWB) can overcome these limitations by allowing III-V growth to occur before integration on Si or in a 3D stack [25]–[28]. The significantly reduced thermal impact, around 200°C lower than selective epitaxy, allows 3D integration of more layers and with a wider range of materials [29], [30]. Many of the technical challenges originally facing DWB have been met, such as integration of large area wafers and reusability of growth substrates [31]. However, a clear understanding of the impact of this integration technique on device performance is still lacking. In this work, we show integration of III-V materials using DWB for both electronics and optoelectronics applications, high-performance transistors and microdisk lasers, and compare these devices

with corresponding ones integrated by other means. Our results indicate that DWB presents a promising path forward for fully integrated III-V devices.

II. HETEROGENOUS INTEGRATION OF III-Vs USING DWB

The basic DWB integration scheme for an unprocessed III-V layer is illustrated in Fig. 2a. The target active III-V layer is grown together with an etch stop layer stack on a donor wafer. The etch stop layer can be the same as or part of the buffer layer if the active layer is grown on e.g. a silicon substrate for cost reasons. For the InGaAs/InP system, typically a stack of an Al-containing compound as well as InP is chosen [32]. The active surface, as well as the target wafer, is coated with an adhesive oxide. The chemistry of the adhesive layer surfaces together with the annealing temperature determines the bonding strength of the interface [27], [33], [34]. Fig. 3a shows the bonding energies of a few common interfaces. A bonding energy of at least 1 J/m^2 is required to achieve a high yield. For III-V integration, the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ interface is a good choice due to the high bonding energy

Fig. 4. (a) Comparison of the on-current at fixed drive bias and off-current, a key logic performance metric, for III-V FinFETs fabricated using similar process flows but integrated by DWB, 3D-DWB and template-assisted epitaxy. (b) High-frequency performance metrics, f_t and f_{max} , comparing III-V FETs, integrated by DWB, 3D-DWB as well as on native III-V substrates to Si RF-CMOS technology. (c) Comparison of three different III-V device designs in order to determine the importance of the two oxide interfaces, the gate oxide interface and the back-oxide interface in III-V MOSFETs integrated on Si by DWB.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF III-V INTEGRATION APPROACHES

Approach	Hybrid technology	On-current ($\mu A/\mu m$)	Integration temperature
DWB	No	350 [6]	250 °C
3D-DWB	Yes	200 [26]	250 °C
TASE	Yes	100 [47]	500 °C
ART	Yes	190 [53]	500 °C
VLS	No	407 [40]	500 °C
Buffer	No	235 [32]	500 °C
Rapid melt	No	N/A	1100 °C
On III-V	No	650 [5]	N/A

at low annealing temperature [33], [35]. With an annealing temperature of only 250 °C, the low thermal impact represents a key benefit of this integration technique and can allow integration of already processed device layers where the gate oxide interfaces require a low thermal budget (typically below 400 °C). After rigorous cleaning, physical contact of the two surfaces and annealing, the donor wafer substrate is removed. This can be done either by wet or dry etching, or mechanically using grinding. Finally, the etch stop layers are carefully removed.

3D integration, i.e. integration of already processed device layers is described next. In sequential 3D integration, shown in Fig. 2b, the device layers are fabricated layer-by-layer. The process flow is similar to the basic integration scheme with the target wafer being an already processed wafer. Since the target surface is no longer that of an epitaxial layer, it must be planarized down to <0.5 nm after deposition of the adhesive layer. Following DWB of the III-V layer, the devices are fabricated sequentially, and the process can be repeated multiple times. The thermal budgets of the device layers must be considered when fabricating the top device layer. While III-V fabrication can be achieved below the thermal budget of Si CMOS (around 500 °C), subsequent fabrication on top of the III-V device layer has a lower thermal budget (below 400 °C) due to sensitivity of the III-V oxide interface. For this reason, low thermal impact device architectures, such as junctionless FETs are interesting for sequential 3D integration of III-Vs [36], [37]. There are two main benefits of sequential 3D integration: Since the bonded layer is unprocessed, there is no alignment required

for the DWB. The alignment accuracy between device layers is instead set by the resolution of the lithography steps in the device fabrication. Furthermore, sequential integration results in identical orientation of the device layers, i.e. a top-to-bottom stacking.

Non-sequential 3D integration is illustrated in Fig. 2c. Here, both the donor and target wafers contain already fabricated device layers. This process has the benefit of having a very low thermal impact (the DWB annealing step, ~ 250 °C), though the alignment accuracy will be lower as it is no longer set by the lithography system, such as a stepper or EBL. Moreover, the bonded device layer ends up upside down. This may be an issue for polarized layers such as GaN as well as for the interlayer metal connect formation. Top-to-bottom orientation can be recovered by the double non-sequential 3D integration scheme shown in Fig. 2d, at the cost of an additional DWB step.

III. INTEGRATED III-V ELECTRONICS

DWB has been successfully leveraged towards integrated III-V nanoelectronics such as high-performance FETs [38], [39]. III-V materials such as indium-rich InGaAs exhibit high electron mobility which can result in MOSFETs with high currents and gains at low operating bias [40]–[43]. In fact, the highest reported gain values for FETs have been reported for InGaAs MOSFETs, with transconductance gain above 3 mS/ μm [40], [43]. Such high transconductance is useful for both logic and high-frequency devices. For the former, the high gain translates to high on-current (a key logic performance metric) at fixed operating bias, where III-Vs have shown the largest reported values to date [5]. For logic applications, integration density is important, and here 3D integration is a promising density booster [24], [26]. The combination of III-V n-type MOSFETs or high-frequency amplifiers with Si CMOS is particularly interesting as it overcomes the typical weakness of III-V electronics in lacking a high-performance PFET [44]. Fig. 3b shows the schematic and TEM image of such a 3D integrated system [45]. The sequential integration approach enables extremely tight co-integration as indicated by the accurate alignment of the top-layer III-V devices

Fig. 5. (a) Vision of integration of III-V optical devices in a Si-CMOS platform within the first interlayer dielectric (ILD0), (b) Illustration of adiabatic optical coupling design from the Si waveguide to the III-V/Si photodetectors using regrown InP. (c) top view micrograph of a III-V photodetector with a lateral-current-collection scheme integrated on Si PIC. The figures in (a-c) are adapted from [78]. (d) Lasing threshold versus temperature (left axis, log plot) for a bonded (square, light blue, filled) and a micro-disk grown directly on Si by Template-Assisted Selective Epitaxy (TASE) (diamond, orange, filled) InP microdisk lasers. The characteristic temperatures are extracted from the linear fit. Emission wavelength (right axis) at different temperatures for the bonded (square, dark blue, empty) and TASE-grown (diamond, brown, empty) lasers. (e) SEM top-view of a directly grown InP microdisk. The dashed line indicates the location of the STEM cross section image on the right. Bonded samples are designed to be identical in terms of geometry.

to the bottom-level Si CMOS device. The low thermal impact of the 3D integration process is demonstrated in Fig. 3c, showing the subthreshold swing of the Si CMOS layer before and after integration [44]. The subthreshold swing is related to the oxide interface, typically the most thermally sensitive part of the FET and the constant slope before and after integration indicates that no significant damage was induced. The total thermal budget here was 300 °C for the 3D-DWB and approximately 500 °C for the III-V MOSFET fabrication.

Fig. 4a compares the on-current at fixed drive bias for III-V FinFETs integrated by DWB, 3D-DWB and template-assisted selective epitaxy (TASE). TASE is a local integration approach where the III-V material is grown into templates, in this example also using aspect-ratio trapping to eliminate defects due to lattice mismatching [46]. Selective epitaxy approaches such as TASE are a fundamentally different integration approach compared to DWB in that they include lattice mismatched growth, typically at temperatures above 500 °C [47]. As the devices in Fig. 4a are fabricated using nearly identical fabrication flows, following the integration of the III-V materials, the comparison of on-current illustrates the challenges associated with each integration approach. DWB exhibits the highest performance, followed by 3D-DWB and TASE, owing to an increased process complexity of the integration and difficulty in maintaining high quality channel material. While DWB and 3D-DWB nominally use a similar integration process, integration on an already fabricated layer is challenging due to the need for highly planarized surfaces and outgassing from the thick encapsulation oxides. Similar holds true for high-frequency III-V MOSFETs. Fig. 4b is comparing the cut-off frequency f_t and maximum oscillation frequency f_{max} of III-V FETs, integrated by DWB, 3D-DWB as

well as on native III-V substrates to Si RF-CMOS technology [7], [48]–[50]. There are also reports of metal-oxide-semiconductor high electron mobility transistors (HEMTs/MOSHEMTs) integrated on Si by DWB showing performance close to that of HEMTs on native III-V substrates [51]. The performance of 3D integrated III-V-on-CMOS is here reported for the first time, showing f_t/f_{max} of 210/200 GHz at $L_G = 25$ nm. The corresponding non-3D III-V-on-Si technology achieved f_t/f_{max} of 370/300 GHz as reported previously [52]. The difference between the two approaches is mainly due to a reduction of the electron mobility in the 3D-DWB devices due to outgassing. Alternative Si integration schemes, such as vertical nanowires grown on III-V buffer layers have resulted in MOSFETs with superior device performance, but a clear path to tight Si CMOS integration is presently missing [40]. A comparison of integration approaches explored in literature is shown in Table I [53]. Hybrid technology refers to if the approach readily can enable tight integration between III-V devices and Si CMOS. The indicated on-current is the highest reported literature value and is an indicator of the III-V material quality and process complexity. The integration temperature is the highest temperature step in the integration process, which is the bonding annealing step for DWB/3D-DWB and the III-V growth for the other approaches (except rapid melt, for which it is the melting step). We note that the overall thermal budget of III-V FETs using DWB is around 500 °C due to the source/drain regrowth, i.e. higher than the integration temperature. This can be overcome using junctionless transistor designs or HEMT structures where the doped contacts are part of the bonded heterostructure [51].

DWB of III-V active layers typically yields a III-V-on-BOX structure, i.e. a thin III-V layer on a buried oxide (on Si substrate).

Therefore, MOSFETs created on such layers will contain two oxide interfaces, the gate-oxide interface and the back-oxide interface. As oxide interfaces tend to be the limiting factor in III-V MOSFET performance (as opposed to Si CMOS) it is important to understand the influence of both oxide interfaces. While the gate-oxide interface has been widely studied, the back-oxide interface has been less so [54], [55]. Fig. 4c shows a study of three types of InGaAs MOSFETs: (i) devices with thin InP barriers separating the InGaAs channel from both oxide interfaces, i.e. creating a quantum well, (ii) devices with only the back-oxide InP barrier and (iii) devices without any InP barriers [52]. The figure shows the on-resistance versus gate length L_G , where the slope of the curve is inversely proportional to the electron mobility. The channel thickness is here around 10 nm. As shown, the quantum well (i) device exhibits approximately 3 times higher electron mobility than both other structures. Additionally, the back-oxide interface offers no clear benefit. The results indicate that the scattering in the device is limited by the gate-oxide interface, likely due to coulomb scattering at charged defects, and that DWB has minimal impact on oxide-related scattering. However, the picture may change for ultrathin-body devices (<5 nm) where the electron wave function extends further into the back-oxide interface [32]. Oxide interface will impact not only mobility through scattering, but also noise levels. Here, more work is needed to elucidate the influence of oxide traps on noise, especially in extremely scaled devices which may be susceptible to noise from single traps [56]–[60].

An emerging application for III-V-on-BOX structures using relatively thin oxides is for high-density dynamic random-access memory cells comprising a single transistor and no capacitor [61]. These memory cells operate by charge storage inside the transistor through back-biasing.

In summary, these results indicate the wide potential of DWB integrated III-V materials for electronics applications. The low process complexity of DWB integration allows the fabrication of FETs with superior performance for both logic and RF, while the low thermal impact enables 3D integration schemes for systems with increased density.

IV. INTEGRATED III-V OPTOELECTRONICS

To meet the ever-increasing global IP traffic [16] there is a need for high-bandwidth and low-power on-chip communication solutions. The electrical interconnects in particular limit future improvements in performance due to power dissipation and cross-talk associated with their downscaling [17], [62]. One way to overcome this interconnect bottleneck is the use of optical interconnects for on-chip optical communication [63]. Co-integration of electronics and photonics would enable high-speed and high-bandwidth communication and increased functionality on chip.

Si photonic integrated circuits (PIC) would offer such a platform while leveraging existing CMOS infrastructures and allowing Si to be used for passive optical components, such as waveguides and splitters, and III-V materials for active devices. Due to their direct and tuneable bandgap, group III-V semiconductors are ideal for efficient lasers, a key component in optical communication. Furthermore, their high absorption coefficients and mobility make them suitable for applications in

Fig. 6. (a) Light-in-light-out curve for a 600 nm wide bonded InP laser without (blue, filled) and with Au cladding (red, empty). Inset: SEM images for the two device configurations. The lines are guides to the eyes. (b) Threshold versus InP cross section for cavities without (blue) and with Au cladding (red) at 300 K (solid line) and 100 K (dashed line).

high-speed photodetectors (PD) at telecommunication wavelengths in the near-infrared (NIR), where Si is transparent.

DWB of III-Vs on Si offers a Si-CMOS-compatible solution for integrated optics with potential for low-cost-high-scalability fabrication. Several optoelectronic devices using wafer bonding have been proposed and demonstrated, from electrically pumped lasers [11], [12], [14], [64]–[70], to modulators [71], [72], amplifiers [73], [74], and PDs with high responsivity or bandwidth [75], [76].

An example of such a hybrid Si /III-V architecture is the photodetector with adiabatic mode coupling and lateral current collection scheme shown in Fig. 5a-c [77], [78]. As illustrated in the schematic in Fig. 5a the III-V layer might be bonded on top of an active silicon wafer containing electronics as well as Si-based waveguides, light can then couple evanescently from the Si waveguiding layer to the III-V active regions above or vice-versa. The Si PIC is fabricated on a SOI, cladded with oxide which is planarized before III-V multi quantum wells (MQW) are bonded via molecular wafer bonding, as is the case for the MOSFETs shown in the previous section. For this case, a low-temperature epitaxial regrowth process (500 °C) was developed for the highly doped p- and n-region for lateral current injection to be compatible with the underlying CMOS platform [31]. The III-V is introduced between front-end-of-the-line (FEOL) and back-end-of-the-line (BEOL), enabling the use of a common BEOL for PICs and CMOS. The devices exhibit sub-nA dark currents, high responsivity and 32 Gbps NRZ transmission [78], [79].

DWB is a state-of-the-art technology to integrate high-quality III-Vs on Si. However, some applications call for a monolithic local integration of active optical components. One way to locally grow single-crystalline III-Vs on Si with a low defect density, despite their lattice, thermal and polarity mismatch is by TASE, as discussed in the previous section for electronic devices [80]. Particularly the possibility for in-plane homo- and hetero-junctions [81] and seamless integration with Si features to form hybrid nanoscale cavities [82] makes TASE attractive for opto-electronic devices.

In [83] identical microdisk lasers fabricated by either DWB or TASE are compared. Fig. 5d shows the lasing threshold and

emission wavelength of a TASE-grown and bonded InP microdisk laser at different temperatures. While at room temperature their performance is very similar, the TASE laser is less temperature-dependent with a characteristic temperature of 190 K, whereas it is 90 K for the DWB integrated device. Fig. 5e shows the top-view SEM and cross-section TEM image of a TASE grown microdisk, showing the sharp sidewalls defined by crystal facets. The different temperature behavior is attributed to the impact of different types of intrinsic defects in the two approaches. The monolithic devices are limited by phase mixing of wurtzite and zincblende, which is a bulk effect and less temperature dependent. The DWB approach provides for high crystal quality material, so the defects here stem mainly from roughness induced in device processing.

There is still a large discrepancy in the size and integration density achievable with electronics and photonics. Downscaling photonics towards the dimensions of electronics is the ultimate goal to achieve greater integration densities and small device capacitance [84]. While 3D integration enables higher device densities, there is also interest in new concepts to scale photonics beyond the diffraction limit of light. One approach is by incorporating metals in the device design to exploit plasmonic resonances and hence bridging the gap between the small-device footprints of electronics and high bandwidth of photonics. The nanoscaled active region volumes may inherently lead to high speed operation with low dark currents [85]–[88]. Moreover, electrically operated nanoscale devices may have metals in the proximity of the gain medium for electrical actuation, irrespective of their capability to support a plasmonic mode. While one would expect increased absorption losses, there are also many benefits connected to the metal, spanning from Purcell enhancement, faster modulation responses [89], increased confinement to improved heat sinking [90]–[92], enabling III-V nanolasers on Si [93]–[96].

In a device-scaling study the impact of metal cladding in optically pumped InP nanodisk lasers bonded on Si is investigated in terms of room-temperature operation and stability at higher pumping powers [97]. Fig. 6a shows the light-in-light-out curve for a hexagonal InP microdisk laser with a cross section width of 600 nm with and without Au cladding. The insets show SEM images of the corresponding devices. The cavity without Au has a lower threshold but degrades for higher pumping powers. Thresholds for different device diameters at 300 K and 100 K are compared in Fig. 6b. Lower thresholds are observed at 300 K for InP-only devices. The Au-cladded cavities, however, show evidence of lasing in much smaller geometries than the InP-only ones. This is attributed to a combination of competing effects in the cavity: The Au introduces ohmic losses which need to be compensated first. At the same time the heat generated inside the gain medium can be effectively dissipated via the metal cladding, while it accumulates in the InP-only device due to the poor thermal conduction of the underlying oxide layer. Therefore, the threshold in the Au-clad devices is higher than for the ones without Au while showing a better performance at higher pumping powers. For smaller cavities increased radiative losses are expected in the InP-only case which, together with the insufficient heat sinking, prevents lasing in that case. At cryogenic temperatures electron-phonon scattering and losses in the metals are reduced and the achievable gain is increased.

We expect that this mitigates the difference in thresholds between both device designs at 100 K.

In summary, DWB offers a Si CMOS compatible integration route for optically active III-V devices for the emission, modulation and detection of light with potentially low power consumption. While the level of fabrication maturity is high and the thermal budget is low for DWB, there is also interest in processing schemes for the local integration of III-Vs on Si such as TASE. Both approaches allow for thin material stacks, lateral current injection, and co-integration with electronic devices, which will be important for short-range optical communication links. Connected to that, plasmon-assisted optoelectronic allow for compact device architectures with metal mediated heatsinking and potential for high-speed and high-bandwidth operation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have examined heterogenous integration of III-V materials using direct wafer bonding technique. This low-temperature integration approach allows III-V materials to retain their high carrier mobilities and enables 3D integration schemes towards dense systems combining multiple functional layers, such as logic, high-frequency and optoelectronics. Both III-V transistors and microdisk lasers integrated by DWB are compared to selective epitaxial approaches. The results indicate that DWB is an attractive approach when performance is a priority over integration density and presents a key path forward for fully integrated III-V electronic and optoelectronic devices.

VI. REFERENCES

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